

OER 2 OEP : A PARADIGM SHIFT

(Open Educational Resources to Open Educational Practices)

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INDIAN INITIATIVES TO OER

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Abstract

Now, in the information technology era, digital resources have become readily accessible source of teaching and learning. One such paradigm shift that encourages and enables promotes such learning resources is Open Educational Resources (OER). In India OER movement is especially significant as higher education is still facing the scarcity of high quality teachers, inadequate infrastructure of the institutions and specifically on their libraries. The paper intends to clarify the use of OER in Indian higher education and to introduce the open educational resources initiatives in Indian education system.

Keywords:

OER (Open Educational Resource), Education system of India

Introduction:

Open educational resources (OER) are unreservedly accessible, openly licensed media, text, and other digital materials that are helpful for teaching-learning process and it also enhance assessing as well as research. It is a paradigm shift in the world of teaching learning and research which facilitates easy access of learning materials with less expense. Such movements are emerging significantly at local, state and national levels. Creative Commons defines (OER) policies as "legislation, institutional policies, and/or funder mandates that lead to the creation, increased use, and/or support for improving OER. OER are learning resources that exist in the public domain or released under an intellectual property that permit free access and repurposing by others.

As William and Flora Hewlett Foundation's definition of OER "OER are the teaching, learning and research resources that reside in the public domain or have been released under an intellectual property license that permits their free use and repurposing by others. OER have modules, textbooks, streaming videos, tests, full courses, course materials, software, and any other tools, materials, or techniques used to support access to knowledge"

Principles of OER:

David Wiley is one of the pioneers of OER. He and colleagues have suggested (Hilton et al., 2010) that there are five core principles of open publishing:

- i. **Re-use:** The most basic level of openness. People are permitted to use all or part of the work for their own purposes for i.e. download an educational video to watch in later.
- ii. **Re-distribute:** People can share the work with others (for example, send a digital article by-email to a colleague).
- iii. **Revise:** People can adapt, modify, translate, or change the work.
- iv. **Re-mix:** People can take two or more existing resources and combine them to create a new resource.
- v. **Retain:** No digital rights management restrictions (DRM); the content is yours to keep, whether you're the author, an instructor using the material, or a student.

Objectives

- To define Open Educational Resources
- To define the Principles of Open Educational Resources
- To exemplify OER initiatives in Indian education system

Methodology

This research paper is based on secondary data. The data has been taken from different websites, journal, research reports and research papers.

Some significant OER initiatives by India**National Repository for of Open Educational Resources (NROER):**

The Central Institute of Educational Technology (CIET), NCERT in collaboration with the Department of School Education and Literacy, Ministry of Human Resource and Development (MHRD), Government of India has developed National Repository for of Open Educational Resources (NROER). Which is powered Gnowledge Labs., Homi Bhaba Centre of Education. The National Repository for of Open Educational Resources lunched for the country in 13th august 2013.
<https://nroer.gov.in/home/repository>

National Programme on Technology Enhanced Learning (NPTEL)

National Programme on Technology Enhanced Learning –NPTEL is a joined initiative of Indian Institutes of Technology and Indian Institutes of Science was initiated (IIT-Bombay, Delhi, Kanpur, Kharagpur, Madras, Guwahati and Roorkee with IIS- Bangalore) which is initiated in 2003. Five disciplines like- civil engineering, computer science and engineering, electrical engineering, electronics, mechanical engineering and communication engineering with the 235 courses in web/video format were developed firstly. The main goal of NPTEL is learning anytime, anywhere by anyone. Now it has approx 1000+ courses available for self-learning. <https://nptel.ac.in/>

SWAYAM:

SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active–Learning for Young Aspiring Minds) is a programme initiated by Government of India and designed to achieve the three cardinal principles of Education Policy viz., access, equity and quality. SWAYAM MOOCs platform is World's Largest Online Free E-Learning Platform Portal designed to achieve the three cardinal principles of Education Policy viz., Access, Equity and Quality by covering School/Vocational, Under-Graduate, Post Graduate, Engineering and Other Professional Courses. <https://swayam.gov.in/>

INFLIBNET:

The INFLIBNET is an autonomous IUC of University Grant Commission, established in 1991 which has headquartered in Gujrat University campus. It becomes an independent IUC in 1996. The main objective is to promote the standard guidelines in the research works, projects to develop new methods and techniques for archival. <https://www.inflibnet.ac.in/library/>

Sakshat:

This portal dedicated to the country for developing teaching and learning for the peoples of the nation. It envisages reaching hitherto deprived sections and rural/under-developed areas and helps in raising the GER in higher education. It supports self-learning through virtual classes by providing by providing a platform for conversation with teachers for two-way interactions through web-based texts, audio and video chats. <http://www.sakshat.ac.in/>

Kalāsampadā:

The Kalasampada have content and information included with a user-friendly interface and developed to encompass and preserve the rare archival collections of the IGNCA. Kalasampada facilitate the users to use and view the resources –a couple of lakh of manuscripts, rare books, thousands of rare photographs, over one lakh slide, audio and video along with highly research publications – of the IGNCA. This one of the strong digital repository in our country. <http://ignca.gov.in/divisionss/cultural-informatics/kalasampada/>

The UGC NET Guide:

This website was launched with a hope to serve as a complete online guide book for UGC NET Examination and give direction to you in a proper way. The solved papers given in this guidebook will help you to become aware of the format of the question papers. The solved question papers given in this website can also be treated as a sample copy. <http://www.netugc.com/>

Vigyan Prasar

It is an autonomous organization under the Department of Science and Technology, Government of India. The Vigyan Prasar promotes science tasks/activities, to encourage and spread scientific and rational outlook, to act as a resource-cum-facility organization for Science & Technology communication. Vigyan Prasar was established in 1989. <https://vigyanprasar.gov.in/>

The Indian National Digital Library in Engineering Sciences and technology Consortium:

INDEST- the Indian National Digital Library in Engineering Sciences & Technology consortium was set up by MHRD in 2003 on the recommendation of an expert group appointed by the ministry to

promote learning and research in the area of engineering and technology in India. The IIT Delhi is the consortium headquarter to organize its activities. <http://paniit.iitd.ac.in/indest/>

CSIR Explorations:

CSIR Unit for Research and Development of Information Products (URDIP) at Pune is the principal agency behind its implementation while Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), Government of India is supporting this project. SIR Explorations is a digital library of electronic dissertations, thesis and research reports of the fellowships and projects supported by CSIR. Presently, it has three bibliographic databases, namely, E-Thesis, EMR (Extramural Research) and CSIR Publications. This database is very useful for the doctoral candidates, faculty members and scientists who are interested in knowing about the researches completed in past by their research fellows.

Cultural Heritage Digital Library in Hindi (CHDLH)

Indira Gandhi National Centre for the Arts (IGNCA), New Delhi, India has established this digital 8 library on indigenous cultural heritage whereas Ministry of Communications and Information Technology, Government of India is supporting it. It promotes the Hindi-speaking province in India. CHDLH disseminates information and traditional knowledge related to: poetic and literary heritage; common heritage of the people; architectural heritage; natural heritage; and miscellaneous information related to other areas of arts, aesthetics and culture.

Digital Library of India

Indian Institute of Science (IISc), Bangalore is the principle agency behind implementation of Digital Library of India. It is hosted at the Mega Scanning Centers Indian Institute of Information Technology Hyderabad (IIIT Hyderabad); Centre for Development of Advanced Computing, Noida (CDAC Noida); Centre for Development of Advanced Computing, Kolkata (CDAC Kolkata) whereas ERNET (Education and Research Network), India is the participating institution in it. Ministry of Communications and Information Technology, Government of India (for India) and National Science Foundation, USA (for Overseas) are supporting agencies behind this project. <http://www.dli.ernet.in/>

in.arXiv

Hosted by Institute of Mathematical Sciences, Chennai (URL 1: <http://in.arxiv.org/> Hosted by IMSc, Chennai) (URL 2: <http://xxx.imsc.res.in/> Hosted by IMSc, Chennai) (URL 3: <http://www.arxiv.org/> Hosted by Cornell University Library, USA) Behind this Digital Library, the Principal Implementing Agency is Institute of Mathematical Sciences, Chennai (IIMSc). It hosts a mirror site of the arXiv, a resourceful open access archive in the fields of physics, mathematics, non-linear science, computer science, quantitative biology and statistics since 1997.

Vidyanidhi

(URL: <http://www.vidyanidhi.org.in/>) Vidyanidhi, a national level repository, covering major universities of India is a national digital library for electronic theses and dissertations (ETD), which is initiated by the University of Mysore and is supported by the Department of Scientific and Industrial Research (DSIR), Ford Foundation and Microsoft India. It aims at enhancing visibility of Indian doctoral research and maintains mainly two kinds of databases namely bibliographic database and full text repository using DSpace software.

<https://ndl.iitkgp.ac.in/document/XmI0TB96cJnEnGkZluCEpYteGne-PwiCTo5qCVH6y3mlfTindroyOZ8Qrg3-RC6dezsc6CdBoBqphoDRnpLi2Q>

CEC Learning Object Repository

The Consortium for Educational Communication (CEC), established by UGC-University Grant Commission, is an inter-university centre on electronic media. The Consortium for Educational Communication create television programmes in a variety of languages for various subjects in harmonization with its 17 Educational Multimedia Research Centers. The television programmes are based on syllabus based topics of the polytechnic, schools, colleges and university levels. Created programmes are broadcasted on the national educational television channels such as Gyan Darshan, Vyas Higher Education Channel and Doordarshan. <http://cec.nic.in/Pages/About-CEC.aspx>

eGyankosh

A National Digital Repository eGyankosh, is a digital repository which is initiated by Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU), New Delhi and is supported by Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India. It stores, index, preserve and share the self instructional study material, audio video programs and radio & television based live interaction sessions, produced by IGNOU. <http://egyankosh.ac.in/>

Conclusion:

Through a common model of open licensing, OER allows anyone to access, customize, and share digitally published educational materials for free, with the end result of advancing teaching and learning worldwide. OER has limitless potential to expand knowledge among lifelong learners around the world. Believing in the capacity of OER, the reach and impact of open courseware needs to be extended by encouraging the adoption and adaptation of open educational materials around the world. The present world demands creativity and innovation from all of us. A culture of learning needs to be developed so as to equip people to prosper in a rapidly evolving, knowledge-based world. A computer-enhanced learning environment can help make the much needed transition from just 'knowing' to 'sharing'. Movement of OER is just started in India. The creation of open education materials in various disciplines by the experts from the institutions of repute will help the teachers to access these materials at the click of the mouse which will help them in classroom teaching. In all, one can say success of OER movement means success for higher education.

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EFFECTIVENESS OF OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES IN DEVELOPING ELECTRONIC TEACHING COMPETENCIES AMONG IN-SERVICE B.Ed., TEACHER TRAINEES

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ABSTRACT

Electronic Teaching involves the use of ICTs to enhance the art of teaching. Online teaching and online learning are becoming very popular these days. Universities and Institutions are offering online courses. Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) from different providers help millions of online learners acquire knowledge almost free of cost. The participants can avail his own free time to learn as it is not time bound. Yet there are areas to explore in the online electronic teaching. E-resources are digital resources that can either be software based or hardware based. Teachers have to make use of some of the open educational resources such as online textbooks, e-dictionaries and animations in the class to support learning process. An experimental study has been undertaken with the following objectives in consideration (1). To identify most important open educational resources that can enhance technical e-teaching competencies (2). To measure the effectiveness of open educational resources in developing electronic teaching competencies. The investigator followed two equivalent group experimental designs for the study. Thirty In-Service B.Ed. teacher trainees studying in K.S.College of Education, Salem, which acts as the B.Ed., learning centre of Alagappa University have been selected for formation of control group and experimental group. Fifteen students for control group and Fifteen for experimental group. The control group was given routine treatment and the experimental group was given treatment using open educational resources. The obtained